

INFLUENCIA EN EUROPA Y AMERICA REVOLUTIONS

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1. INTRODUCTION

With the declaration of independence of the United States, a small cycle of revolutions will be produced as a consequence that will come to link with the French Revolution. Chronologically we can establish it between 1780 and 1789, more specifically between the Signing of the PEACE OF VERSAILLES (1783) AND the FEDERAL CONSTITUTION (1789). We see, therefore, a quite evident link between the American process and this small cycle of mobilizations. There is that influence that comes to act on an ill-being, restlessness and already existing claims.

2. COMMON FEATURES

- They pose, many times, still in an embryonic form, a series of demands or alternatives that are within liberal ideas, emanating from rationalism and that are also in connection with nationalist bases, being a precedent of the two great approaches origin of the processes revolutionaries that will take place later.
- Frustrated movements, which did not achieve their objectives. They failed in their mobilizations, many of them came to fail through foreign intervention, being the precedent of interventionist policies to eliminate any liberal movement (Congress of Vienna - 1815).
- We cannot forget the role that the reformist policy carried out by the European monarchies at that time will play - Enlightened Despotism. Trigger in certain types of movements.
- Decades or years of economic fluctuations, being another factor of certain influence.

It is therefore about mobilizations of a certain complexity, especially in the case of Spanish America, because it simultaneously poses a double aspect, existing, therefore, traditional movements and innovative movements.

3.2 SPANISH AMERICA: What is happening in North America will have a strong impact on the rest of the continent, it is also or is a continent dependent on other powers.

The first geographical space where we will find this type of movement will be South America, constituting a precedent for the independence movements that began in 1808 (Spanish Independence) and culminated around 1823. It is, therefore, a colonial empire, with a strong dependence economic and administrative of the metropolis, since it controls the political-administrative mechanisms and institutions. These structures are quite outdated, expired and are also taken over by Spaniards who arrive from the peninsula (hence the name they receive - peninsulares) by the government with the basic and primary objective of enriching themselves, the minority task being to carry out the functions for which they were entrusted. , make up a closed oligarchy. Below we find CRIOLLOS middle sectors (descendants of Spaniards but born in American lands) who seek greater participation in the political field that is forbidden to them because it is reserved for the Spanish. It is a society where there is an absolute domain of the peninsular, although they constitute a small number of people, where the bourgeois sector - Creole is postponed to administrative aristocracy.

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Economically speaking, we are facing a mercantilist monopoly regime, always for the benefit of the metropolis fundamentally, this does not mean that the Creoles do not experience development, but it is true that the ultimate control is in the hands of the Spanish. These are sectors that seek greater economic freedom that falls to their own benefit.

These sectors are aware of the currents and approaches carried out on the European continent - Racionalism, therefore, ideologically they are driven to raise these claims.

There will be certain movements that respond to a liberal-national mobilization model, but we must not forget that the complexity of this geographical framework is that they tend to mix with traditional movements. These outbreaks come, in most cases determined by the Reform Policies carried out by Carlos III derived from the principles of enlightened despotism. These measures of change will also constitute another factor in this entire process, complex and embryonic of localized and brief but significant movements with respect to what would happen later.

The mobilizations can focus on the Viceroyalty of New Granada or Peru, they will take place in the chronological framework in which the war of independence of the United States takes place, without having finished it, but with signs of an early end.

3. THREE TYPES OF MOVEMENTS

- Impulses encouraged by some of the reform policies of Carlos III, with an eminently popular character, where the aim is to restore the previous situation (Tupac Amaru).
- Fiscal pressure (Comuneros).
- Movements that respond to nationalist liberalism (Francisco Miranda Movement in Caracas).

None of these movements achieved the proposed objectives, partly because they were suffocated and also because of the loss in many cases of the initial impulse.

October 30, 1998

- EUROPE:
- IRELAND: Chronologically it is earlier, it is also a case of great importance since even today it is not fully resolved.

With the constitution of the national states, there will be an agglutination that has England as its axis, but that incorporates Scotland and Ireland, forming what was called Great Britain, a long, costly and complicated process, especially in the case of Ireland due to religious issues (Anglicanism - Catholicism).

Ireland's situation is one of dependence on England, which some historians have called semi-colonialism, because since the 17th century Ireland has been subject to two pressures: the pressure exerted from London and the pressure exerted by the dominant Protestant oligarchy on the population. Catholic. There is a progressive dismantling of the Irish productive framework, for which its trade is reduced, being reduced to an internal framework, if to this we add the fact that the land, a source of wealth and prestige, is in the hands of the Protestant oligarchy and that the Dublin parliament does not have its own powers but is subject to that of London. We can understand how the mobilizations arise. It will be the war of independence, a conjunctural factor, which will make the protest movement jump, because England is forced to send its troops to North America to support the existing troops there. But leaving the island unguarded, which the Catholics took advantage of. A defense front is promoted - Militia Program - of the island against possible French attacks, at first it could only be formed by Protestants, but given their small number they allow the adhesion of Catholics, this will be used to claim greater participation not only political but also economic, this will be well seen by the oligarchy, so they will maintain a common front. The problem stems from the intention of Catholics to promote or demand equal rights with respect to Protestants, which will cause the common front that had been formed to dissolve, thus being one of the key factors in the failure of the movement. In addition to this we must add that after the signing of the Peace of Versailles the troops begin to return to their original locations.

During the rest of the century and afterwards sparks of restlessness will resurface (1789) and from that moment on, and in an increasingly structured way, a movement will develop that will gradually take on greater importance.

SWITZERLAND: Agitation materialized in Geneva, where one of the simplest and, in turn, shorter movements of the period we are analyzing will take place. In the Canton of Geneva there is a government dominated by an increasingly closed

or rigid oligarchy - clan. It tries to take over larger plots of power, strengthen its powers and exert greater pressure on society. There is an expanding middle sector, which has undergone significant development, especially in manufacturing, and which is also strongly ideological (Rousseau). Sectors convinced that in 1782 they will rise up against that ruling oligarchy, getting it out of power, but this victory will not last long, since troops will be sent from other cantons and France to restore the balance.

3.3.3 NETHERLANDS AND BELGIUM:

The Netherlands until the end of the 16th century depended on the Spanish crown. It is known that they were a constant headache for the existing monarchies due to their resistance to Spanish rule. Much more pronounced in the North (Holland).

HOLLAND: It became independent at the end of the 16th century.

BELGIUM: It remained attached to the empire until the war of Spanish succession. In 1713 the PEACE OF UTRECHT was signed, by which Spain lost most of its possessions in Europe, Belgium passed with this treaty to depend on Austria.

HOLLAND: It is governed by the ORANGE, in this case William V, it is not a monarchy but a kind of regency - ESTATUDER. This raises the strengthening and concentration of their powers, that is, becoming a monarch. On the other hand, we find a minority sector made up of the aristocracy that dominates the local administration, a sector frequently linked to family ties, which do not accept this claim. We have a third group or sector made up of merchants, liberal professions and artisans who make up the middle classes influenced by the ideas of the time in which there is a desire to achieve greater equality. At the economic level, we are in a stage of clear economic contraction, reduction in trade and rise in prices, that is, a crisis that mainly affects the popular sectors. A common front of collaboration will be established against the claims of the Estatuder, united by their rejection. They will unite their efforts getting William V thrown out and forced into exile. But as the challenge of movements that we have analyzed is frustrated due to the external intervention carried out by the Prussians, they send an army to restore the situation.

BELGIUM: It depends, as we said before, on the Austrian Empire, in this case on the monarchy of Joseph II, a monarchy of a reformist nature, where a series of fundamentally centralizing but also reformist measures are attempted. This will be what will act as an impulse, being the nobility - aristocracy joining with the sectors of the middle bourgeoisie and labor sectors which are affected by the increase in prices, especially of wheat and, consequently, increase in the precariousness of life. Those who will rise up to expel the Austrian troops that settled in the territory to become the UNITED BELGIAN STATES (Clear influence of the North American process). This movement was frustrated due, firstly, to the fact that once the objective was achieved, there would be a disagreement between the conjunctural allies, causing internal ruptures that would favor the forwarding of the Austrian troops and, consequently, the restoration of order. An issue that was not resolved until 1830, which is when it will definitively achieve its independence.

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